

Some Mixed Ligand Thiocyanato Complexes of Cobalt(II)

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Dithiocyanato bis(thiourea) cobalt(II) complex was reacted with a variety of ligands containing nitrogen donor atom in a mixed solvent medium. The following mixed ligand complexes were isolated and characterised by analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infrared and electronic spectroscopy. $[\text{Co}(\text{tu})_2(\text{SCN})_2\text{L}_2]$ where L = pyridine, aniline, piperidine, *p*-toluidine and *p*-anisidine; $[\text{Co}(\text{tu})_2(\text{SCN})_2\text{L}_1]$ where L = 3-methyl pyridine, 4-methyl pyridine and isoquinoline and $[\text{Co}(\text{tu})_2(\text{SCN})_2\text{L}]$ where L = ethylenediamine. They are weak electrolytes and paramagnetic.

As a part of a series of investigations on mixed ligand complexes of transition metals, we have undertaken studied on d^7 metal complexes. Thiourea complexes of divalent cobalt were studied for the first time by Rosenheim and Meyer¹ and later on by several other workers²⁻⁴. Cotton *et al.* reported two complexes of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{tu})_2\text{X}_2]$ where tu = thiourea and X = Cl⁻ and Br⁻. In this communication we report some mixed ligand thiocyanato cobalt(II) complexes.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Dithiocyanato bis-(thiourea) cobalt(II) was prepared by refluxing Co(II) thiocyanate with thiourea in 1 : 2 molar ratio in ethanol for one hour. On cooling, crystalline compounds separated out. It was suction filtered and dried.

carbon tetrachloride. On refluxing for 30 min and cooling, crystalline compounds separated out. These were suction filtered and dried in vacuo. The method of preparation was almost identical in all the cases.

The purity of the complexes was established by estimating the metal and the thiocyanate by standard methods. The conductance measurements were carried out using a 'Toshniwal' Conductivity Bridge, Type CI 0102 and a conventional cell, previously calibrated with aqueous potassium chloride solution. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at room temperature over solid specimens using 'GOUY' balance. Infrared absorption spectra of the compounds were recorded using UNICAM SP-200 Spectrophotometer. The analytical, conductance and magnetic moment data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE I—ANALYSIS, MELTING POINTS, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF COBALT(II)

Compound	Colour & form	M.P. (°C)	% Cobalt		% Thiocyanate		% Nitrogen		Λ_M mho/cm ²	μ_{eff} B.M.
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.		
$[\text{Co}(\text{tu})_2(4\text{-MePy})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	Pink crystalline	180	8.23	8.43	16.42	16.60	19.87	20.28	35	4.91
$[\text{Co}(\text{tu})_2(3\text{-MePy})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	-do-	147	8.17	8.43	16.40	16.60	19.91	20.28	36	4.86
$[\text{Co}(\text{tu})_2(\text{Py})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	-do-	195	12.05	12.15	23.82	23.92	22.76	23.09	53	5.04
$[\text{Co}(\text{tu})_2(\text{L.Q.})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	-do-	181	9.93	10.07	19.60	19.83	16.23	16.61	36	4.76
$[\text{Co}(\text{tu})_2(\text{Aniline})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	-do-	270	11.13	11.49	22.42	22.61	21.34	21.83	60	4.68
$[\text{Co}(\text{tu})_2(p\text{-Toluidine})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	Brown amorphous	270*	10.45	10.89	21.20	21.44	20.25	20.76	60	4.76
$[\text{Co}(\text{tu})_2(\text{en})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	-do-	127	15.04	15.23	29.80	29.97	28.36	28.94	69	4.76
$[\text{Co}(\text{tu})_2(\text{Piperidine})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	-do-	270*	11.62	11.86	23.12	23.34	22.17	22.53	55	4.90
$[\text{Co}(\text{tu})_2(p\text{-anisidine})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	-do-	135	10.02	10.28	20.02	20.24	19.72	20.10	60	4.84

* Denotes decomposition.

To the hot ethanolic solution of dithiocyanato bis-(thiourea) cobalt(II) complex, requisite amounts (1 : 2 ratio) of nitrogen donor ligands were added separately followed by addition of a few ml. of

Results and Discussion

Divalent cobalt ion can form tetra-, penta-, or hexa-coordinated complexes depending on the

structure and polarisability of the ligand and experimental conditions. The present investigations assume a special significance in stabilising the preferred coordination number since different ligands with varying electronegativities of the donor atom are involved in competition to coordinate with the metal ion. They are all spin free and the magnetic measurements indicate the presence of three unpaired electrons. The higher values are due to orbital contribution. It is evident that magnetic moments can not distinguish between tetra-, hexa- and octa-coordination. The presence of coordinated ligands as found by analysis and i.r. spectra rules out the possibility of tetra-coordination. The coordination number of the metal ion can be six in $\text{CoL}_4\text{tu}_2(\text{SCN})_2$, where L = 3-methyl pyridino, 4-methyl pyridino and isoquinoline, provided the thiocyanate remains in the ionic state outside the coordination sphere. Even for 1:1 electrolytes the Λ_M values in acetone medium will be as high as 150 mhos⁵ and the low values obtained by using M/1000 solutions show that they are only very weak electrolytes. Hence for the complexes $\text{Co}(\gamma\text{-Pic})_4\text{tu}_2(\text{SCN})_2$, $\text{Co}(\beta\text{-Pic})_4\text{tu}_2(\text{SCN})_2$ and $\text{Co}(\text{I.Q.})_4\text{tu}_2(\text{SCN})_2$, the hexa-coordination is ruled out.

The infrared spectra of the complexes are recorded in Table 2. Strong absorption bands of both thiourea and the nitrogen ligands used are present indicating definitely that they are mixed ligand complexes. As expected the ligand absorption bands are modified as a result of bonding to the metal. Some bands are, however, masked in the absorption range of Nujol used as the mulling agent. Rao *et al.*⁶ have shown the existence of metal to sulphur bond rather than metal to nitrogen bond in the thiourea complexes of Co(II) and some other transition metals.

other workers^{10,11,7} at 1476 cm^{-1} in free thiourea represents the N-C-N mode. This band is expected to be sensitive to coordination through sulphur and is likely to be shifted to higher frequency region because of the increased double bond characters of the C-N bond. In the case of Nitu₄Cl₂ Oliff¹² noticed this band at 1500 cm^{-1} . In the present case also the band appears near about 1490 cm^{-1} indicating a shift to higher frequency region. The C=N band frequency of the complexes as given in Table 2 show a definite shift from its value in the free heterocyclic bases thus indicating the bonding to the metal ion.

The thiocyanate ion NCS^- is an ambidentate ligand and the features of its coordination behaviour have been reviewed recently^{13,14}. In the present case, very sharp bands were observed in the region 2050–2100 cm^{-1} . Terminal and bridging thiocyanate groups have been distinguished^{15–16} earlier and accordingly there are only terminal groups in the compounds reported. Turco¹⁷ has distinguished between frequencies for M-SCN and M-NCS compounds. The compounds reported here seem to possess M-NCS groups.

In the visible absorption spectrum of cobalt(II) complexes two bands were observed around 8000 and 18500 cm^{-1} region. Three bands should appear for an octahedral cobalt(II) complex due to $4T_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow 4T_{2g}(\nu_2)$, $4T_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow 4T_{1g}(\text{P})(\nu_3)$ and $4T_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow 4A_{2g}$ transition. The bands observed in the present case are attributable to first two transitions. The $4T_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow 4A_{2g}$ transition being due to a two electron process appears as a weak band in the high frequency side of $4T_{1g}(\text{P})$. This weakness, combined with closeness to $4T_{1g}(\text{P})$ transition renders it unobserved in the present case. Hence the complexes have an octahedral configuration.

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRA OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF COBALT(II) (CM^{-1})

Complex	(C-S)*	(C=C)*	(C=N)*	N-C-N* bending	NH ₂ * rocking	(C-N)* of thiocyanate
$[\text{Cot}_2(4\text{-MePy})_4(\text{SCN})_2]$	710	1620	1635	1490	1060	2050
$[\text{Cot}_2(3\text{-MePy})_4(\text{SCN})_2]$	715	1610	1635	1495	1055	2100
$[\text{Cot}_2(\text{Py})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	730	1600	1630	1495	1055	2080
$[\text{Cot}_2(\text{I.Q.})_4(\text{SCN})_2]$	730	1618	1640	1480	1030	2050
$[\text{Cot}_2(\text{An})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	725	1600	1630	1490	1040	2100
$[\text{Cot}_2(p\text{-Toluidine})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	720	1610	1635	1485	1070	2080
$[\text{Cot}_2\text{en}(\text{SCN})_2]$	720	1615	1640	1490	1080	2060
$[\text{Cot}_2(\text{Piperidine})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	730	1618	1645	1500	1085	2080
$[\text{Cot}_2(p\text{-Anisidine})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	720	1610	1630	1500	1080	2100

* All the bands are very sharp.

Irving *et al.*⁷ have argued that the band at 730 cm^{-1} (thiourea) was mainly due to C-S stretching and this shifted consistently to lower frequency region forming metal sulphur bond. This position also prevails when nitrogen and sulphur coordinates to metal ion as reported⁹ in the case of some metal complexes of N-N'-bis(α -pyridyl)thiourea. Lowering of the frequencies of the C-S stretching vibrations indicate⁹ weakening of the C=S bond. The band found by

The octa-coordinated complexes possibly dissociate in acetone solution to give hexa-coordinated octahedral species as evidenced from the electronic spectra. In absence of any previous work on the electronic spectra of octa-coordinated complexes which belong to either D_{4d} or D_{2d} symmetry class when the cube is distorted, it is difficult to differentiate them from octahedral in solution state.

However, it is not difficult to distinguish the donor molecules which are actually coordinated and which are simply trapped in the lattice from the study of characteristic absorption bands in the i.r. spectra as in case of coordinated molecules the bands will be very much affected than in the case of un-coordinated molecules. When such a difference in the pattern is not observed in the i.r. spectra, it is presumed that all the four ligand molecules are coordinated to give octa-coordinated complex.

From analytical, spectral, magnetic and conductance evidence, the mixed ligand complexes now reported fall under two categories : (i) hexa-coordinated, and (ii) octa-coordinated. The former category can be represented by the formula $\text{CoL}_2\text{tu}_2(\text{SCN})_2$ where L = pyridine, aniline, *p*-toluidine, piperidine and *p*-anisidine. The complex : $\text{CoL}_2\text{en}(\text{SCN})_2$ is also hexa-coordinated. The compounds $\text{Co}(4\text{-Mepy})_4\text{tu}_2(\text{SCN})_2$, $\text{Co}(3\text{-Mepy})_4\text{tu}_2(\text{SCN})_2$ and $\text{Co}(\text{I.Q.})_4\text{tu}_2(\text{SCN})_2$ are presumably octa-coordinated.

However, only X-ray crystallographic studies on these compounds will be able to establish the exact stereochemistry.

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References

1. A. ROSENHEIM and V. J. MEYER, *Z. Anorg. Chem.*, 1906, **49**, 13.
2. M. NARDELLI, L. CAVALCA and A. BRAIBANTI, *Gazz. Chim. ital.*, 1957, **87**, 917.
3. M. NARDELLI, L. CAVALCA and G. FAVA, *Gazz. Chim. ital.*, 1957, **87**, 1209.
4. F. A. COTTON, O. D. FAUT and J. T. MAQUE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 17.
5. R. A. ROBINSON and R. N. STOKES, "Electrolytic Solution", Butterworth Publ. (Lond.), 1959, Ed.
6. K. C. DASH, M. ALI, R. N. PATEL and D. V. RAMAN RAO, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 246.
7. K. SWAMINATHAN and H. M. N. H. IRVING, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1962, **26**, 1291.
8. D. BANERJE and I. P. SINGH, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1968, **6**, 34.
9. A. V. MALLIK, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 1743.
10. R. W. OLIFF, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 2037.
11. B. K. MAHAPATRA and D. V. RAMAN RAO, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 284.
12. R. W. OLIFF, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 2037.
13. J. L. BURMEISTER, *Coordination Chem. Rev.*, 1966, **1**, 205 and 1968, **3**, 225.
14. A. H. NORBURY and A. I. P. SINHA, *Quart. Rev.*, 1970, **24**, 69.
15. K. C. DASH and D. V. RAMAN RAO, *Curr. Sci.*, 1966, **35**, 462.
16. J. CHEAT and L. A. DUNCANSON, *Nature*, 1956, **178**, 997.
17. A. TURCO and C. PECILE, *Nature*, 1961, **191**, 66.